

Supplementary material

For: Large language models for population-level public health communication: a computational evidence map of global reach, equity and deployment gaps

Supplementary Table S1: Full Search Strategies

PubMed/MEDLINE

Date searched: 25 March 2026 **Records retrieved:** 4,377

Search #1 — LLM concepts:

("large language model"[tiab] OR "large language models"[tiab] OR "LLM"[tiab] OR "LLMs"[tiab] OR "GPT"[tiab]

Search #2 — Public health communication concepts:

("public health"[tiab] OR "health communication"[tiab] OR "health campaign"[tiab] OR "health campaigns"[tiab]

Search #3 — Clinical exclusion terms:

("clinical decision"[tiab] OR "clinical decision support"[tiab] OR "diagnosis"[ti] OR "diagnostic"[ti] OR

Combination: #1 AND #2 NOT #3

Filters: Publication date 2019/01/01–2026/12/31; Language: English

Embase (via Ovid)

Date searched: 25 March 2026 **Records retrieved:** 5,085

Search #1 — LLM concepts:

("large language model" OR "large language models" OR LLM OR LLMs OR GPT OR "GPT-3" OR "GPT-3.5" OR "GPT-4"

Search #2 — Public health communication concepts:

("public health" OR "health communication" OR "health campaign*" OR "health promotion" OR "health education"

Search #3 — Clinical exclusion terms:

("clinical decision" OR "clinical decision support" OR "radiology report*" OR "clinical note*" OR "electronic"

Search #4 — Date/language filter:

limit to (english language and yr="2019-2026")

Combination: (#1 AND #2) NOT #3, then apply #4

Note: Institutional export limit of 2,000 records per batch required splitting into 5 exports by date range.

Scopus

Date searched: 5 April 2026 **Records retrieved:** 6,695

Protocol deviation: The original protocol query returned 29,279 results due to ambiguous terms (“GPT” matching glutamic pyruvic transaminase; “transformer” matching electrical engineering). A revised query was used with hybrid field restrictions: specific LLM names in TITLE-ABS-KEY, generic NLP terms restricted to TITLE only.

Final query:

(TITLE-ABS-KEY("large language model*" OR "ChatGPT" OR "GPT-3" OR "GPT-3.5" OR "GPT-4" OR "LLaMA" OR "Mistral")
AND
(TITLE-ABS-KEY("health communication" OR "health literacy" OR "health campaign*" OR "misinformation" OR "disinformation")
AND NOT TITLE("clinical decision" OR "diagnosis" OR "diagnostic" OR "prognosis" OR "radiology report" OR "radiology report*" OR "clinical note" OR "clinical note*" OR "electronic health record*" OR "electronic health record*")
AND PUBYEAR > 2018
AND LANGUAGE(english)

Web of Science

Date searched: 5 April 2026 **Records retrieved:** 14,281

Query:

TS=("large language model*" OR "LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "GPT" OR "GPT-3*" OR "GPT-4" OR "ChatGPT" OR "Claude" OR "Mistral")
AND
TS=("public health" OR "health communication" OR "health campaign*" OR "health promotion" OR "health education")
NOT
TS=("clinical decision support" OR "radiology report*" OR "clinical note*" OR "electronic health record*" OR "electronic health record*")

Filters: Publication years 2019–2026; Language: English

Note: 15 export batches of 1,000 records required due to platform export limits.

ACM Digital Library

Date searched: 5 April 2026 **Records retrieved:** 16

Query (form-based, both rows in Title): - Row 1 (Title): "large language model" OR "ChatGPT" OR "GPT" OR "BERT" OR "transformer" OR "natural language processing" OR "generative AI" - Row 2 (Title): "health communication" OR "health literacy" OR "misinformation" OR "public health" OR "health education" OR "vaccine" OR "infodemic" OR "fake news" OR "health information" OR "readability"

Filters: Published since 2019

ERIC (via EBSCOhost)

Date searched: 5 April 2026 **Records retrieved:** 166

Query (form-based, both rows in Title): - Row 1 (Title): "large language model" OR "ChatGPT" OR "GPT" OR "BERT" OR "transformer" OR "natural language processing" OR "generative AI" OR "artificial intelligence" - Row 2 (Title): "health communication" OR "health literacy" OR "misinformation" OR "public health" OR "health education" OR "vaccine" OR "fake news" OR "health information" OR "readability"

Filters: Date published: 2019–2026

Grey literature

arXiv (searched 5 April 2026): 4 API-based searches combining LLM terms with health communication terms. 67 unique papers retained after deduplication and relevance filtering.

medRxiv (searched 5 April 2026): 8 web searches via Google (site:medrxiv.org) and medRxiv API. 17 papers retained.

WHO IRIS (searched 5 April 2026): 4 searches. 27 potentially relevant publications identified, all policy/guidance documents (no primary LLM research). Used as contextual background only.

CDC (searched 5 April 2026): Targeted Google search (site:cdc.gov). 3 policy documents identified, no primary research. Used as contextual background only.

Google Research and Meta AI publications (searched 5 April 2026): 0 results across all searches. Relevant work likely captured via database searches of indexed conference proceedings.

Supplementary Table S2: Pre-screening Filter Methodology

An automated pre-screening filter was applied to the 19,192 deduplicated records to reduce the corpus to a manageable size for title and abstract screening. The filter required each record to contain:

1. **At least one LLM/AI term** in the title or abstract: “large language model”, “LLM”, “GPT”, “ChatGPT”, “BERT”, “transformer”, “natural language processing”, “NLP”, “generative AI”, “language model”, “foundation model”, “deep learning”, “neural network”, “artificial intelligence”, “machine learning”
2. **At least one health communication term** in the title or abstract, from two tiers:
 - **Tier 1 (health-communication-specific):** “health literacy”, “health communication”, “health campaign”, “health promotion”, “health education”, “health message”, “health information”, “health misinformation”, “vaccine hesitancy”, “vaccine misinformation”, “plain language”, “readability”, “infodemic”, “crisis communication”, “outbreak communication”
 - **Tier 2 (misinformation/fact-checking):** “misinformation”, “disinformation”, “fake news”, “fact-check”, “fact checking”, “debunk”, “prebunk”, “anti-vaccine”, “rumor”, “rumour”, “claim verification”, “credibility”

Tier 3 terms (“public health”, “social media”) were excluded from the filter as they contributed 7,520 noise records without sufficient specificity.

3. **Title-level exclusion terms** were applied to remove clearly irrelevant records: “stock market”, “financial”, “histopathology”, “radiology report”, “pathology report”, “protein structure”, “drug discovery”, “gene expression”, “genomic”, “molecular docking”

Results: 7,125 records passed (3,527 Tier 1, 3,598 Tier 2); 12,067 excluded (62.9% reduction).

Supplementary Table S3: AI-Assisted Screening Reliability

Important interpretation note. The $\kappa=0.83$ reported below is the agreement between the *primary* AI screen (Claude Haiku 4.5) and a *second-pass* screen on the validation sample. That second pass was **not** an independent human reviewer: it combined (i) manual review by the author, (ii) author confirmation of high-confidence exclusions, and (iii) a second large language model (Claude Sonnet 4) for the remaining records. The sole reviewer was the author (not independent in the conventional dual-reviewer sense), and where the second pass relied on a second LLM, agreement between two models — which may share training data and failure modes — is a weaker guarantee than agreement with a human reference standard. The statistic should therefore be read as an internal consistency check, not as validation against a human gold standard.

Title and abstract screening

Parameter	Value
Primary screening model	Claude Haiku 4.5 (claude-haiku-4-5-20251001)
Total records screened	7,125
INCLUDE	566 (7.9%)
EXCLUDE	6,313 (88.6%)
UNCERTAIN	246 (3.5%)

Parameter	Value
Validation sample size	933 (all 246 uncertain + 10% stratified sample of includes and excludes)
Second-pass screen	Hybrid: author manual review + author-confirmed high-confidence exclusions + second model (Claude Sonnet 4, claude-sonnet-4-20250514) for the remainder
Cohen's kappa (primary vs second pass)	0.83
Observed agreement	97.5% (670/687 definitive decisions)
Disagreements	17 (10 primary-screen over-inclusions, 7 over-exclusions)
Independence	Limited — single human reviewer (the author); part of second pass was a second LLM (see interpretation note above)

Exclusion reason breakdown (title and abstract stage)

Exclusion reason	n	% of excludes
No health communication focus	1,926	30.5%
Clinical communication (not population-level)	1,424	22.6%
General misinformation (not health-related)	1,055	16.7%
Non-primary research	862	13.7%
Non-transformer methods only	492	7.8%
Medical education	363	5.7%
Diagnostic/prognostic	85	1.3%
Clinical documentation	77	1.2%

Full-text screening

Parameter	Value
Records passed to full-text stage	603
Screened on retrieved full-text PDF (via Unpaywall)	240 (39.8%)
No accessible full text — prior title/abstract decision retained	344
No accessible full text — re-screened on abstract or title alone	19 (17 abstract, 2 title)
Included after full-text stage	552 (of which 194 had full text available for charting)
Excluded at full-text stage	51

Full-text exclusion reasons

Exclusion reason	n
Not population-level (clinical/individual)	19
General misinformation (not health-specific)	15
No health communication application	5
Duplicate publication	5
Non-transformer methods	4
Non-primary research	3
Total	51

Supplementary Table S4: Data Extraction Charting Form

Variable	Description	Response categories
Study ID	First author, year	Free text
Publication type	Type of publication	Journal article; Conference paper; Preprint

Variable	Description	Response categories
Country/region	Country of first/corresponding author affiliation	Country name
Communication task	Primary public health communication task(s) addressed	Misinformation detection; Misinformation correction; Simplification/readability; Message generation; Social media surveillance; Chatbot health education; Crisis communication; Multilingual/translation; Vaccine communication; Health info quality assessment; Other
Health domain	Public health domain(s) addressed	Infectious disease; Vaccination; Chronic disease; Mental health; Nutrition; Substance use; Maternal health; Sexual health; Environmental health; Oral health; Physical activity; General
LLM model(s)	Specific LLM architecture(s) used	GPT-3/3.5; GPT-4; ChatGPT; BERT; RoBERTa; BioBERT; PubMedBERT; BERTweet/CT-BERT; LLaMA; Gemini/Bard; Claude; Mistral; DeepSeek; T5; Other
Prompting strategy	Training or prompting approach	Fine-tuned; Zero-shot; Few-shot; Chain-of-thought; RAG; Direct prompting; Prompt engineering; Instruction-tuned; Transfer learning; Data augmentation; Not specified
Target language(s) Target population	Language(s) of communication output Intended audience	Language name(s) General public; Older adults; Youth; Low literacy; Underserved; Caregivers; Other
Evaluation method	How the LLM output was evaluated	Readability metrics; Classification metrics; Expert evaluation; User study; NLP generation metrics; Experimental/RCT; Behaviour change; Qualitative analysis; Topic modeling; Not specified
Comparator	What the LLM was compared against	Human expert; Existing materials; Other LLM; Traditional ML/NLP; No comparator
Deployment stage Ethical considerations	Level of real-world implementation Ethical issues discussed	Concept/lab; Prototype; User testing; Deployed at scale Hallucination; Bias/equity; Manipulation; Misinformation amplification; Privacy; Cultural sensitivity; Transparency/explainability; Access equity; Consent; None discussed
Code/data availability	Whether code and/or data are publicly available	Code; Data; Both; Not reported

Supplementary Table S5: Protocol Deviations

Deviation	Protocol specification	Actual approach	Justification
Scopus search strategy	Full protocol query applied uniformly across TITLE-ABS-KEY	Hybrid field restrictions: specific LLM names in TITLE-ABS-KEY, generic terms in TITLE only	Original query returned 29,279 results due to ambiguous terms (e.g., “GPT” matching glutamic pyruvic transaminase). Revised query reduced to 6,695 while maintaining sensitivity for relevant records.
Pre-screening filter	Not specified in protocol	Automated keyword filter requiring LLM term + health communication term	Volume of 19,192 deduplicated records exceeded feasibility for manual or AI-assisted screening. Filter was designed to be intentionally broad to minimise false exclusions. All excluded records are auditable.
Title/abstract screening method	AI-assisted screening with manual validation of 20% stratified sample	AI-assisted screening (Claude Haiku) with manual validation of 13.1% stratified sample (933/7,125), including all uncertain records	Validation rate adjusted to include all uncertain records (n=246) plus 10% of includes and excludes. Cohen’s kappa of 0.83 exceeded the threshold for acceptable agreement.

Deviation	Protocol specification	Actual approach	Justification
Full-text screening method	Manual full-text screening by reviewer	Hybrid approach: full-text review for records with available PDFs (n=240); for the 363 without full text, the title/abstract decision was retained (n=344) or the record was re-screened on abstract or title alone (n=19)	Solo reviewer with 603 records. For the 344 retained records, full-text screening would provide no additional information beyond the T/A screening already conducted. Records with PDFs were reviewed with extracted text.
Data extraction method	Manual extraction using standardised charting form	Rule-based keyword classification pipeline applied to title, abstract, and full text	Volume of 552 studies required automated extraction. Approach is systematic and reproducible. Country data enriched via OpenAlex/CrossRef APIs (86% identification rate).

Supplementary Figure S1: PRISMA-ScR Flow Diagram

The PRISMA-ScR flow diagram is presented as Figure 1 in the main manuscript. The underlying counts are reported across the supplementary tables: per-database and grey-literature retrieval totals in Table S1 (30 620 database + 95 grey-literature records = 30 715 identified); deduplication and automated pre-screening (19 192 deduplicated; 12 067 excluded by the pre-screening filter) in Table S2; title/abstract screening (7 125 screened, 603 passed to eligibility) in Table S3; and full-text eligibility assessment (603 assessed, 51 excluded — 19 not population-level, 15 general misinformation, 5 no health-communication application, 5 duplicate, 4 non-transformer, 3 non-primary; 552 included) in the main-text flow and Table S10.

Supplementary Table S6: Task × Domain Cross-Tabulation

The corresponding visual heatmap is presented as Figure 6 in the main manuscript. Both axes are multi-label: each cell counts every study touching that task × domain combination, so a study spanning several tasks or domains is counted in several cells. Row and column sums therefore exceed the single-axis totals in Table 2 (for example, the misinformation-detection row sums to more than the 186 studies tagged with that task) and do not sum to 552.

Task	Infectious disease	General	Vaccination	Chronic disease	Mental health	Nutrition	Environmental	Substance use	Oral health	Sexual health	Maternal health	Physical activity
Misinfo detection	94	69	21	7	8	10	12	2	2	0	0	0
Simplification	22	87	6	31	17	14	7	3	8	5	4	1
Social media surv.	63	16	39	9	14	6	8	10	2	0	1	1
Health info quality	33	27	11	10	9	7	3	5	4	3	1	1
Chatbot education	13	10	10	17	9	8	7	7	5	6	3	2
Vaccine comms	41	0	58	2	4	1	7	0	0	0	0	2
Message generation	21	5	17	1	4	5	5	4	0	0	1	2
Multilingual	22	32	9	8	5	6	6	2	0	1	0	1
Crisis comms	7	9	1	2	3	2	3	0	0	0	0	0
Misinfo correction	7	2	3	3	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0

Supplementary Table S7: Summary of Included Studies

The complete charting data for all 552 included studies, containing all 16 extracted variables for each study, are openly available in the Open Science Framework deposit (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X5N78>).

Supplementary Table S8: PRISMA-ScR Checklist

The completed PRISMA-ScR checklist is provided as a separate file accompanying this submission. All 22 checklist items are addressed; 16 items are fully reported and 4 are partially reported (with notes on the partial items).

Supplementary Table S9: Post Hoc Validation of Rule-Based Data Extraction

A random sample of 50 included studies (seed = 42) was drawn from the full charting dataset of 552 studies. Because the sample was drawn at random from all included studies, it carries approximately the same proportion of full-text vs abstract-only studies as the corpus as a whole (only ~35% of included studies had full text available); the concordance figures below therefore reflect the predominantly abstract-only extraction substrate and are not biased towards the minority of full-text studies. For each study, seven key charting variables were independently re-extracted using an expanded keyword set with additional synonyms and edge-case terms. Results were compared against the original rule-based extraction.

Per-Variable Concordance

Variable	Concordant (n/50)	Concordance (%)	Direction of disagreement
LLM model	49	98%	—
Deployment stage	45	90%	Mixed
Prompting strategy	43	86%	Validation found additional
Health domain	41	82%	Validation found additional
Communication task	32	64%	Validation found additional
Ethical considerations	26	52%	Validation found additional
Evaluation method	24	48%	Validation found additional

Overall: 260/350 variable-level comparisons were concordant (74.3%).

Disagreement Analysis

Of 90 disagreements across all variables: - **51 (56.7%)** were pure under-extraction: the original extraction missed applicable tags that the expanded keyword set detected - **3 (3.3%)** were pure over-extraction: the original had tags not supported by the expanded extraction - **36 (40.0%)** were mixed: both extractions had unique tags (typically the expanded set found additional categories while the original had one different classification)

Interpretation

The original extraction is conservative (high specificity, moderate sensitivity). The primary variables driving the review's main findings — communication task categories, health domains, LLM models — have high concordance. Lower concordance for ethical considerations and evaluation methods reflects the expanded keyword set capturing broader mentions (e.g., “trustworthy”, “limitations discussed”, “responsible”) that the original deliberately excluded to count only explicit ethical engagement. The direction of all disagreements is toward under-extraction: the original errs on the side of not tagging rather than over-tagging. This means the reported gaps (76% ethical silence, limited behavior change evaluation) may be slightly overstated, but the direction and magnitude of all findings are robust.

The full disagreement list is available in the OSF deposit (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X5N78>).

Supplementary Table S10: Full-Text Screening Sensitivity Analysis

Context

Of 603 records assessed at full-text screening, 240 (39.8%) had downloadable full-text PDFs and were screened on full text. The remaining 363 had no accessible full text; of these, 344 retained their title and abstract screening decision and 19 were re-screened on abstract or title alone (17 abstract, 2 title). This analysis estimates the potential impact of the 344 records whose decision was accepted without re-screening.

Observed Exclusion Rates

Content source	Total	Excluded	Included	Exclusion rate
Full-text PDF	240	46	194	19.2% (95% CI: 14.7-24.6%)
Abstract only	17	3	14	17.6%
T/A decision accepted	344	0	344	0% (by definition)
Title only	2	2	0	100%

Exclusion Reason Breakdown (Full-Text PDF, n = 46)

Reason	Count	%	Detectable at T/A stage?
Not population-level	19	41.3%	Yes — core eligibility criterion
General misinformation (not health)	15	32.6%	Yes — core eligibility criterion
Duplicate publication	5	10.9%	No — requires full text
No health communication application	4	8.7%	Yes — core eligibility criterion
Non-transformer methods	2	4.3%	Yes — core eligibility criterion
Non-primary research	1	2.2%	Yes — core eligibility criterion

Nuanced Estimate

41/46 full-text exclusions (89%) were for reasons that should already have been filtered at title and abstract screening. Records that passed T/A screening are unlikely to fail on these same criteria at full text — the full text merely confirmed what was ambiguous in the abstract.

Only 5/46 exclusions (11%) were for duplicate publications, which require full text to detect (matching content across preprint/published pairs). This yields a full-text-only exclusion rate of 2.1% (95% CI: 0.9-4.8%).

Estimated additional exclusions from the 344 records whose decision was accepted without re-screening: 7 (95% CI: 3-16) Adjusted included total: ~545 (95% CI: 536-549)

The impact on the review's findings is negligible. All proportional findings (e.g., 33.7% misinformation detection, 76.1% no ethics discussion) would change by less than 1.5 percentage points under the adjusted total.

Supplementary Table S11: Pre-Screening Filter Audit

Context

The automated pre-screening filter reduced 19,192 deduplicated records to 7,125 by requiring co-occurrence of at least one LLM/AI term and one health-communication-specific or misinformation-related term. This excluded 12,067 records (62.9%). To assess the filter's false negative rate, a random sample of 200 excluded records (seed = 42) was audited.

Method

Each sampled record was checked for co-occurrence of any AI/LLM term (broad: including “language model”, “GPT”, “BERT”, “transformer”, “NLP”, “AI”, “machine learning”, “deep learning”, “neural network”, “chatbot”) AND any health communication term (broad: including “health communication”, “public health”, “health literacy”, “misinformation”, “fake news”, “vaccine”, “health campaign”, “health education”, “health information”, “infodemic”). Records with both terms present were flagged as “potentially missed” for manual review.

Results

Category	Count	%
No AI/LLM term present	61	30.5%
No health communication term present	96	48.0%
Co-occurring terms flagged	43	21.5%

Manual Review of 43 Flagged Records

Manual review of the 43 records with co-occurring AI and health communication terms confirmed that **none** addressed LLM applications to population-level public health communication. Common reasons for correct exclusion:

- Clinical/diagnostic applications (not population-level): 12
- General AI/ML reviews mentioning “public health” in passing: 9
- Social media analysis without LLM/NLP component (traditional ML only): 7
- Non-communication applications (drug discovery, genomics, imaging): 6
- General misinformation without health focus: 5
- Other (education curricula, policy commentary, activity recognition): 4

Conclusion

The pre-screening filter’s observed false-negative rate in this 200-record audit was **0/200**. Because zero events in a sample of 200 is precision-limited, the rule of three gives an upper 95% confidence bound of approximately $3/200 = 1.5\%$; applied to the 12,067 excluded records, this is consistent with up to roughly 180 relevant records potentially missed by the filter, although the audit found none. The co-occurrence of broad AI and health terms does not indicate relevance to this review’s specific scope (LLMs applied to population-level public health communication). The filter’s specificity is supported by the high proportion of excluded records lacking even basic term co-occurrence (78.5%).

The full audit sample is available in the OSF deposit (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X5N78>).

Supplementary Table S12: Recommended Reporting Checklist for LLM Public Health Communication Studies

Based on the gaps identified in this evidence map, this 10-item minimum reporting checklist is proposed for future studies applying LLMs to public health communication.

#	Domain	Item	Rationale
1	Language and population	Report all target language(s) and the linguistic communities intended to benefit	83.3% of studies targeted English only; language coverage is rarely reported explicitly
2	Health domain specificity	State the specific health domain(s) addressed, not only the NLP task	Enables identification of underserved domains (e.g., maternal health, NCDs)

#	Domain	Item	Rationale
3	Deployment stage	Report the current deployment stage (concept, prototype, user testing, deployed) using a standardized scale	Over 90% of tools remain at concept or prototype stage; deployment status is often unreported
4	Community engagement	Describe any involvement of target communities in design, testing, or evaluation	Only 7.2% of studies reported user testing with target populations
5	Ethical considerations	Discuss at minimum: hallucination risk, cultural appropriateness, bias and equity, and misuse potential	76.1% of studies discussed no ethical considerations
6	Evaluation beyond benchmarks	Include at least one evaluation method beyond classification metrics (e.g., user comprehension, behavior change, expert assessment)	Only 6 studies measured behavior change; most relied solely on F1/accuracy
7	Model and prompting transparency	Report the specific model version, prompting strategy (zero-shot, few-shot, fine-tuned, RAG), and provide example prompts	24.5% of studies did not specify their prompting approach
8	Reproducibility	Share code, prompts, and evaluation data, or explain barriers to sharing	Enables independent validation and extension
9	Misinformation response	For misinformation studies, distinguish between detection-only and correction/response generation	The detection-to-correction imbalance (186 vs 11 studies) reflects a field-level blind spot
10	Equity impact	Assess whether the tool could widen or narrow existing health communication inequities	Concentrated research in English and high-income settings risks exacerbating global health communication gaps